

USING INTERACTIVE TECHNOLOGIES TO TEACH A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. The article is devoted to the relevance of interactive technologies in a higher education setting, and the most effective interactive strategies that can be used in a classroom with a purpose of developing communicative competence and personal growth. In fact, the value of utilizing interactive technologies in the teaching and learning process is assessed.

Keywords: interactive technology, interactive method, communication, dialogue, discussion, brainstorming, case, project, role play, presentation.

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ДЛЯ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

Аннотация. Статья посвящена актуальности интерактивных технологий в условиях высшего образования и наиболее эффективным интерактивным стратегиям, которые могут быть использованы в аудитории с целью развития коммуникативной компетентности и личностного роста. Фактически, оценивается ценность использования интерактивных технологий в процессе преподавания и обучения.

Ключевые слова: интерактивная технология, интерактивный метод, коммуникация, диалог, дискуссия, мозговой штурм, кейс, проект, ролевая игра, презентация.

Nowadays, there is a significant transition from passive to active learning. As a result, significant emphasis is placed on enhancing the technology components of specialized training and adopting a process-centered approach to learning in which the student actively engages in cognitive activity.

Using interactive technologies in the classroom is one approach to achieve these objectives. It aids in the growth of pupils' imagination and creativity, as well as their ability to communicate and enthusiasm in learning foreign languages. The phrase "interactive learning technology" is typically associated with computer or multimedia learning because it suggests direct messaging and interactive conversation with actual partners.

Interactive methods, tools, and forms that stimulate learning, as well as cognitive and mental circumstances and processes for obtaining targeted objectives are all part of interactive learning technologies. As a result, a teacher can use a variety of engaging techniques thanks to interactive technology.

Interactive foreign language teaching technology is based on an activity-based approach and includes the use of interactive teaching methods, including non-situational (dialogue) and situational (games, simulations, situation analysis, bidding ideas, etc.); organic combination in the educational process of various learning tools (electronic and paper information), innovative forms of education (distance learning) and traditions of the full principles of implementations and complement each other. The basis of interactive learning is direct dialogue between students - teachers, students - students, students - guests. This can be a single lesson, a series of lessons, or an entire course.

Interactive technology is characterized by the presence of dialogue, exchange of ideas, discussion of the pros and cons of issues. Discussion lessons are effective if participants have a basic knowledge of the topic and if the teacher has planned the main phases and key points in advance. During the planning stage, the teacher selects and develops a topic and plans how to stimulate and monitor participant activity.

He must prepare the necessary equipment to record the students' ideas. Once the discussion begins, the teacher will act as the facilitator. It is very important to be able to recognize different points of view on a particular issue, have your own opinion, draw conclusions and evaluate success. You can use various techniques to introduce your topic to your audience. Describe a problematic situation, ask a problematic question, show a video, role-play a situation, or give an opinion on a topic. Discussions should include different perspectives and ultimately a decision will be made.

One of the most effective activities is having class discussions about different topics. Discussions on career-related topics will help students communicate in their future workplaces and enrich their vocabulary in specific fields. Teachers should involve students in discussions after reading articles and texts related to future work. Teachers organize and facilitate discussion by formulating questions, pointing out interesting and original ideas or conflicting topics, and helping resolve disagreements.

Interactive technology is based on interactive communication between students and teachers, so the learning process involves all students in cognitive activities. It means that an exchange of ideas, knowledge and experiences takes place. By participating in interactive activities, students learn collaboration, logical thinking, information analysis, and problem solving. The necessary prerequisites for effective language learning are free communication, expression of opinions, and mutual respect.

Concluded that the introduction of interactive technology into the university educational process improves students' communication skills and increases their motivation. Develop personal, intellectual and social skills. Create a positive atmosphere in your class. Students need to be competitive in their future career fields.

Mastering the English language is one of the priorities for any professional. The modern world requires the strengthening of the general cultural foundations of education and the development of skills that activate individuals' abilities to deal with social problems. What is needed are highly professional graduates who not only follow instructions, but also have creative and constructive potential.

It is clear that there cannot be a universal scheme for organizing the learning process. The structure of the lesson varies depending on the purpose, content, target group, etc. The use of interactive technology is not an end in itself, but a means of creating the necessary conditions for communicative and effective learning.

Promotes individual cooperation and self-development, improving both foreign language communication skills and personality traits

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